

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO SCHOOLCHILDREN WITH MODERN COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

Nurniyazov Nursultan

Nukus State pedagogical institute named after Ajiniyaz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8122272>

Abstract: *This article highlights the great importance given to foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the innovative technologies necessary for learning them.*

Keywords: *foreign language, game, innovative technology, technological tools, methods, methods.*

After our country gained independence, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Currently, teaching foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. Today, there is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. As a logical continuation of these thoughts, the Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012 expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages.

In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them.

Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also provides for increasing the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways.

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies. Possible.

Reference:

- 1.: Bekmuratova U. B. Abstract on the topic "Using innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent - 2012
2. Otaboeva, M. R. The use of modern innovative technologies in foreign language teaching and its effectiveness / M. R. Otaboeva. — Text: neposredstvennyy, elektronnyy // Molodoy uchenyy. — 2017. — No. 4.2 (138.2). — S. 36–37. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/138/39058/> (data obrashcheniya: 27.04.2020)
- 3.N. Q. Khatamova, M. N. Mirzayeva. "INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS" (methodical guide), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages.
4. M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rikhsittilayeva. "USE OF HELPING TOOLS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE". Tashkent: TDPU named after Nizomi, 2005
- 5.O. Hoshimov, I. Yakubov. "ENGLISH TEACHING METHODOLOGY" (study guide) Tashkent: "Sharq" publishing house, 2003